

Impulse Response Approximation for Arbitrary Sampling Rate Conversion

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ABSTRACT

Converting a digital signal from one sampling rate to another, where the according clocks are independent of each other, is revisited. The state-of-the-art approach approximates an ideal continuous impulse response in a suboptimal manner. For a new approach an ideal impulse response is specified and approximated with a polynomial according to a least squares-criterion. This approach is compared with the state-of-the-art approach concerning expenditure: storage and multiplication.

1 Introduction

Often the necessity arises to convert a digital signal (Fig.1) from one sample rate f_{S1} to another f_{S2} , mainly for two reasons: *i*) To reduce the computational burden, the signal is converted to the minimal sample rate, given by the sampling theorem. *ii*) The sample rates are defined by different standards, e.g. the sample rate for digital television [4] is 17.7 MHz for PAL, Europe, or 14.3 MHz for NTSC, USA.

If the sample rates are related by a fixed rational factor, a common fractional sample rate converter [3] consisting of an upsampler, filter and downsampler can be utilized. The ratio of the up- and downsampling factors must be equal to the desired conversion factor f_{S2}/f_{S1} . If the sample rates are derived from two different clock generators (as in the above example of digital television), the conversion factor may be any arbitrary even slowly time-varying number. Then the principles of asynchronous sample rate conversion (ASRC) must be applied allowing a variable conversion factor.

In Fig.1, ASRC is depicted with the input signal $x(t_{1,k})$ and the output signal $y(t_{2,n})$, where both may not be strictly equidistantly sampled. Since there is no restriction on $t_{2,n}$, the aim of the ASRC is to optimally approximate a corresponding time-continuous signal $x_c(t)$ in compliance with a given criterion. In case of a slowly time-varying input clock, we subsequently assume $x(t_{1,k}) = x(kT_1)$, with $T_1 = \text{const.}$, at least for the (finite) memory of the ASRC system.

*This work was supported by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft under contract GO 849/1-1.

Figure 1: Principle of ASRC

Figure 2: A widespread method for ASRC

A widespread approach [5, 7] to ASRC is depicted in Fig.2. It consists of three parts: 1) a digital interpolator (L -fold upsampler and filter $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$), 2) a continuous interpolator, to be implemented as polynomial interpolation of order n_{Pol} (in Fig.2: Sample/Hold), and 3) a sampler operating at the output rate f_{S2} . This method can also be interpreted as polynomial interpolation of the impulse response $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ [7]. As a result, the cascade of the digital and continuous interpolators is completely described by the overall continuous impulse response $h_{\text{ASRC}}(t)$, and the output signal of the ASRC system is readily obtained by convolution:

$$y(t) = \sum_{\forall k} h_{\text{ASRC}}(t - kT_1)x(kT_1). \quad (1)$$

Fig.3 shows an example, where the dots represent the impulse response $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$. Using $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ as time do-

main samples for continuous interpolation, where the design of $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ is related to $f_s = \frac{L}{T_1}$, and connecting them, for instance, linearly, a continuous overall impulse response $h_{\text{ASRC}}(t)$ is obtained.

Since the precalculated coefficients $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ are stored in a look-up-table, $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ must be an FIR-filter. So the only coefficients to be determined in real time are those of the polynomial interpolation. Obviously, in order to achieve a prescribed performance, a trade-off between the order n_{Pol} of the polynomial interpolation and the upsampling factor L can be made, requiring little (much) storage and much (little) computation or well-balanced minimum expenditure, respectively [4, 5].

Figure 3: Linear interpolation of $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$

This state-of-the-art approach to ASRC suffers from two fundamental deficiencies: *i*) It tacitly assumes that $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ represents the optimal equidistant samples of a desired continuous impulse response $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$. *ii*) Between the samples $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ no information about $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ exists.

In order to overcome the above deficiencies a novel approach to the design of a finite-length continuous impulse response for ASRC is proposed: First a desired impulse response is defined on a dense time grid t_λ by truncating and sampling of an ideal impulse response $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ (sect. 2). Then (in sect. 3) the coefficients a_μ of the polynomial

$$h_{\text{ASRC}}(t) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{n_{\text{App}}} a_\mu t^\mu, \quad (2)$$

are determined subject to the minimization of the squared error:

$$\sum_{\forall t_\lambda} |e(t_\lambda)|^2 = \sum_{\forall t_\lambda} |h_{\text{ASRC}}(t_\lambda) - h_{\text{ideal}}(t_\lambda)|^2. \quad (3)$$

Finally the resulting approximation error and the expenditure are compared with those of the state-of-the-art approach for different n_{Pol} (sect. 4).

2 Ideal Impulse response $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$

The desired impulse response $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ is required to meet the following conditions (Fig.4):

- Its frequency response $H_{\text{ideal}}(j\omega)$ must be of the lowpass type [7].
- $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ is of finite length, $t \in [-T_0, T_0]$, as $h_{\text{ASRC}}(t)$ for the state-of-the-art approach.
- $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ is symmetric. So its frequency response $H_{\text{ideal}}(j\omega)$ has a linear phase.
- The interpolation condition, $y(\kappa T_1) = x(\kappa T_1)$, requires

$$h_{\text{ideal}}(\kappa T_1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } \kappa = 0, \\ 0, & \text{for } \kappa \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

This equation can easily be derived by setting of $t = \kappa T_1$ in (1).

Figure 4: Example for $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$

For the design of $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ on the time grid $t_\lambda = \lambda \frac{T_1}{L_{\text{Grid}}}$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{K} = \{-\frac{n_{\text{grid}}}{2}, \dots, \frac{n_{\text{grid}}}{2}\}$, with the filter order n_{grid} , every L_{grid} th band filter [6] (with linear phase) design method is suitable. The necessary filter order n_{grid} can easily be derived with the help of Fig.3 and Fig.4 as $n_{\text{grid}} = 2 \lfloor L_{\text{grid}} \frac{T_0}{T_1} \rfloor$. The filter design method in [1] is chosen, where the continuous impulse response of a lowpass with a specified transition band is given by:

$$h_{\text{ideal}}(t) = \frac{\sin(\omega_0 t)}{\omega_0 t} \left(\frac{\sin(\Delta\omega t/2p)}{\Delta\omega t/2p} \right)^p. \quad (5)$$

In contrast to other design methods the impulse response can easily be calculated even for a large L_{grid} , by setting $t = t_\lambda$ in (5). For infinite length, the impulse response represents an ideal lowpass:

$$H_{\text{ideal}}(j\omega) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } \omega \leq \omega_0 - \frac{\Delta\omega}{2}, \\ 0, & \text{for } \omega \geq \omega_0 + \frac{\Delta\omega}{2}. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The truncation of $h_{\text{ideal}}(t_\lambda)$ leads to the best approximation of the ideal lowpass in (6) for a continuous least squares criterion [1]. As a parameter the relative pass band edge $\alpha = (\omega_0 - \Delta\omega/2)T_1/\pi$ ($\alpha = 1$ represents $\frac{f_{s1}}{2}$) is used. The other parameters are: $\frac{T_0}{T_1}$, the relative length, and p , which specifies the form of the transition band [1]. It is observed that the truncation error for a given α and $\frac{T_0}{T_1}$ can be minimized by a suitable choice of $p \in \mathbb{R}$.

3 Least Squares Approximation subject to Equality Constraints

The l_2 -norm of the error (3) is to be minimized but in addition the interpolation condition (4) must be met:

$$h_{\text{ASRC}}(t_\lambda) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{n_{\text{App}}} a_\mu t_\lambda^\mu \stackrel{!}{=} h_{\text{ideal}}(t_\lambda) \quad (7)$$

for $t_\lambda = \kappa T_1$. All λ , which hold $t_\lambda = \kappa T_1$, are arranged in the set $\mathbb{K}_{\text{eq}}$, the remaining λ in $\mathbb{K}_{\text{rest}} = \mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{K}_{\text{eq}}$. The l_2 -norm to be minimized is then given by

$$\sum_{\lambda \in \mathbb{K}_{\text{rest}}} |e(t_\lambda)|^2 = \sum_{\lambda \in \mathbb{K}_{\text{rest}}} |h_{\text{ideal}}(t_\lambda) - \sum_{\mu=0}^{n_{\text{App}}} a_\mu t_\lambda^\mu|^2. \quad (8)$$

The equality constraints in (7) can only be met, if the number $n_{\text{App}} + 1$ of coefficients a_μ is greater or equal to the number N_{eq} (the length of $\mathbb{K}_{\text{eq}}$) of equality constraints. Subsequently this case is assumed.

To minimize the l_2 -norm (8) under consideration of the equality constraints, (7) must be introduced into (8). Therefore (7) is rearranged to

$$\sum_{\mu=0}^{N_{\text{eq}}-1} a_\mu t_\lambda^\mu + \sum_{\mu=N_{\text{eq}}}^{n_{\text{App}}} a_\mu t_\lambda^\mu = h_{\text{ideal}}(t_\lambda), \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{K}_{\text{eq}}, \quad (9)$$

written in matrix notation as

$$\mathbf{F}_1 \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{F}_2 \mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{h}_{\text{ideal}}^{\text{eq}} \quad (10)$$

with

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = [a_0, \dots, a_{N_{\text{eq}}-1}]^T, \quad \mathbf{a}_2 = [a_{N_{\text{eq}}}, \dots, a_{n_{\text{App}}}]^T, \quad (11)$$

$$[\mathbf{F}_1]_{\lambda, \mu} = t_\lambda^\mu, \quad \mu \in [0, \dots, N_{\text{eq}} - 1], \quad (12)$$

$$[\mathbf{F}_2]_{\lambda, \mu} = t_\lambda^\mu, \quad \mu \in [N_{\text{eq}}, \dots, n_{\text{App}}], \quad (13)$$

and $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}_{\text{eq}}$. Solving (10) for $\mathbf{a}_1$ yields

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = \mathbf{F}_1^{-1} (\mathbf{h}_{\text{ideal}}^{\text{eq}} - \mathbf{F}_2 \mathbf{a}_2). \quad (14)$$

Next the error for $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}_{\text{rest}}$ is also rearranged corresponding to (9):

$$e(t_\lambda) = \sum_{\mu=0}^{N_{\text{eq}}-1} a_\mu t_\lambda^\mu + \sum_{\mu=N_{\text{eq}}}^{n_{\text{App}}} a_\mu t_\lambda^\mu - h_{\text{ideal}}(t_\lambda), \quad (15)$$

written in matrix notation:

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{a}_2 - \mathbf{h}_{\text{ideal}}^{\text{rest}} \quad (16)$$

with $\mathbf{T}_1$ and $\mathbf{T}_2$ as $\mathbf{F}_1$ (12) and $\mathbf{F}_2$ (13), but with $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}_{\text{rest}}$. After replacing $\mathbf{a}_1$ with (14) the l_2 -norm (8), in matrix notation $\mathbf{e}^T \mathbf{e}$, is minimized with respect to $\mathbf{a}_2$. After some calculations we get

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{F}_1^{-1} \mathbf{F}_2 - \mathbf{T}_2)^T (\mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{F}_1^{-1} \mathbf{F}_2 - \mathbf{T}_2) \mathbf{a}_2 \\ & = (\mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{F}_1^{-1} \mathbf{F}_2 - \mathbf{T}_2)^T (\mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{F}_1^{-1} \mathbf{h}_{\text{ideal}}^{\text{eq}} - \mathbf{h}_{\text{ideal}}^{\text{rest}}). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Now $\mathbf{a}_2$ can be computed, and then $\mathbf{a}_1$ by (14). For $n_{\text{App}} > 15$ the matrix, which must be inverted to solve (17), is ill conditioned. A CHOLESKY decomposition of the matrix could improve this.

method	storage	mult.	tv. m.
state-of-the-art	$(n_{\text{Pol}} + 1)^2 + \frac{n_{\text{Dig}}}{2} + 1$	$(n_{\text{Pol}} + 1)^2$	n_{Pol}
approx.	$n_{\text{App}} + 1$	$n_{\text{App}} + 1$	n_{App}

Table 1: Expenditure of the two methods

4 Design Example and Comparison

The parameters of the state-of-the-art approach are L and n_{Pol} . The order n_{Dig} of $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ is: $2 \lfloor L \frac{T_0}{T_1} \rfloor$ (Fig.3+4). The chosen design method for $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ is the same as for $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ [1], so this method will have no error at $t_\lambda = \kappa \frac{T_0}{T_1}, \kappa \in \mathbb{Z}$. Other design methods for $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ lead to a considerably higher approximation error. The only parameter of the proposed method is the order n_{App} of approximation.

Figure 5: FARROW-structure

A measure of the expenditure is the required storage and number of multipliers to calculate one sample $h_{\text{ASRC}}(\Delta t)$ in (1), where $\Delta t = t_{2,n} - kT_1$. The number of time-varying (tv) multipliers to calculate $(\Delta t)^\mu$ in (2) is determined on the basis of a FARROW-structure (Fig.5) [2]. The required storage and number of multipliers for the proposed method can easily be derived from Fig.5 and is noted in Tab.1. The state-of-the-art approach needs $n_{\text{Dig}}/2 + 1$ registers (using the coefficient symmetry of linear phase filters) for $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ and $(n_{\text{Pol}} + 1)^2$ for the polynomial interpolation, because every coefficient of the interpolating polynomial is a polynomial of Δt of order n_{Pol} . For $h_{\text{Dig}}(\nu)$ no multiplier is required, because its coefficients are the input signal of the polynomial interpolation.

To compare the expenditure of both methods, L is chosen for a given n_{Pol} and n_{App} , so that the l_2 -error (excluding the truncation error) for both methods is nearly the same. Some typical examples are given in Tab.2 and 3. The case $n_{\text{Pol}} = 0$ is excluded, because the required L is very close to L_{grid} . p is numerically computed such that the truncation error is minimized.

For a large number of test cases it can be stated, that for small $n_{\text{Pol}} (< 3)$ the state-of-the-art approach requires considerably more storage (especially for $n_{\text{Pol}} = 0$) but less multiplications than the other method. For greater n_{Pol} the required storage does not decrease anymore, although the number of multipliers increases. So the trade-off, mentioned in the introduction, between

n_{App}		l_2 -error	stor.	mult.	tv. m.
10		1.58e-6	11	11	10
n_{Pol}	L				
1	53	1.57e-6	164	4	1
2	16	1.31e-6	58	9	2
3	8	1.35e-6	41	16	3
4	5	5.95e-6	41	25	4
4	6	9.25e-7	44	25	4
n_{App}		l_2 -error	stor.	mult.	tv. m.
12		8.59e-9	13	13	12
n_{Pol}	L				
2	37	8.56e-9	121	9	2
3	15	9.02e-9	62	16	3
4	10	5.20e-9	56	25	4

Table 2: Expenditure for $T_0/T_1 = 3$, $\alpha = 0.8$, $p = 0.788$, $L_{\text{grid}} = 200$

n_{App}		l_2 -error	stor.	mult.	tv. m.
12		2.10e-4	13	13	12
n_{Pol}	L				
1	16	1.98e-4	85	4	1
2	7	1.87e-4	45	9	2
3	4	3.20e-4	37	16	3
n_{App}		l_2 -error	stor.	mult.	tv. m.
14		1.41e-5	15	15	14
n_{Pol}	L				
1	30	1.60e-5	155	4	1
2	11	1.26e-5	65	9	2
3	6	1.31e-5	47	16	3

Table 3: Expenditure for $T_0/T_1 = 5$, $\alpha = 0.8$, $p = 1.292$, $L_{\text{grid}} = 200$

storage and computation is not valid and the proposed method is favorable. A larger relative length $\frac{T_0}{T_1}$ leads on the one hand to a reduction of the truncation error but on the other hand due to a more complicated $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ to an increased approximation error.

5 Conclusion

The case of asynchronous sampling rate conversion (ASRC) was revisited. It was shown that the state-of-the-art approach approximates an ideal continuous impulse response in a suboptimal manner. An ideal impulse response is specified and approximated by a polynomial applying a least squares criterion with additional equality constraints. This new approach is compared with the state-of-the-art approach concerning expenditure in storage and computation. For a realization of an ASRC, where less multipliers might be necessary and the storage does not matter, the state-of-the-art approach with $n_{\text{Pol}} \leq 1$ is recommended. For other cases the method by approximation is better suited.

For an equiripple approximation of $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ with equality constraints (7), which minimizes the l_∞ -norm: $\max_{t \in \lambda} |e(t_\lambda)|$, similar results are obtained. Instead of the approximation of $h_{\text{ideal}}(t)$ a frequency domain approximation of $H_{\text{ideal}}(j\omega)$, defined in (6), with a polynomial as in (2) is desirable. Current investigations deal with this problem and must be compared to [8, 9], where this task is already examined.

Acknowledgment

The author wishes to express his appreciation to Prof. Dr.-Ing. H. G. Gökler for his careful review of the manuscript and valuable suggestions.

References

- [1] C. S. Burrus, A. W. Soewito, R. A. Gopinath, *Least Squared Error Filter Design with Transition Bands*, IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing, 40:1327-1340, June 1992.
- [2] C. W. Farrow, *A Continuously Variable Digital Delay Element*, ISCAS'88, Helsinki, Finland, 3:2641-2645, June 1988.
- [3] H. G. Gökler, *Polyphase Realization of Fractional Sample Rate Converters*, ECCTD'99, Stresa, Italy, 1:405-408, September 1999.
- [4] T. I. Laakso, V. Valimäki, J. Henriksson, *Tunable Downsampling Using Fractional Delay Filters with Application to Digital TV Transmission*, ICASSP'95, Detroit, Michigan, 2:1304-1307, May 1995.
- [5] R. Lagadec, D. Pelloni, D. Weiss, *A 2-Channel, 16-bit Digital Sampling Frequency Converter for Professional Digital Audio*, ICASSP'82, 1:93-96, Paris, France, May 1982.
- [6] F. Mintzer, *On Half-band, Third-Band, and Nth Band FIR-Filters and Their Design*, IEEE Trans. on Acoustics, Speech, Signal Processing, ASSP-30:734-738, October 1982.
- [7] T. A. Ramstad, *Digital Methods for Conversion Between Arbitrary-Sampling Frequencies*, IEEE Trans. on Acoustics, Speech, Signal Processing, ASSP-3:577-591, June 1984.
- [8] J. Vesma, T. Saramäki, *Interpolation Filters with Arbitrary Frequency Response for All-Digital Receivers*, ISCAS'96, Atlanta, 2:568-571, May 1996.
- [9] J. Vesma, R. Hamila, T. Saramäki, M. Renfors, *Design of Polynomial Interpolation Filters based on Taylor Series*, EUSIPCO'98, Rhodes, Greece, 2:568-571, September 1998.